

USING FLAX FIBRES AND SHIVES IN SANDWICH STRUCTURES FOR TRANSPORT APPLICATIONS

S. Essid¹, L. Bizet¹ and A. Saouab¹

¹ LOMC, UMR CNRS 6294, Université Le Havre Normandie, Le Havre, France

S. Essid (safa.essid@univ-lehavre.fr)

L. Bizet (laurent.bizet@univ-lehavre.fr)

A. Saouab (abdelghani.saouab@univ-lehavre.fr)

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ABSTRACT

This article presents an experimental investigation of quasi-static bending behaviour of an innovative flax based sandwich structure. The skins and core were made respectively of flax fibres reinforced bio-based epoxy (GreenPoxy56) and flax shives particleboard with two different shives sizes. The skins and core were elaborated respectively by vacuum infusion method and thermo-compression. Then, mechanical characterization of each component of sandwich structures was performed. Two different elaboration processes, thermo-compression and vacuum bag molding were used to elaborate flax based sandwich structures. Then, the influence of each shives size and manufacturing technique on sandwich bending behavior was discussed. The failure of the different sandwich was also analyzed. The reference material used for comparison consists in a sandwich structure made of a commercial honeycomb core (Nidaplast 8 RI) and glass fibres reinforced unsaturated polyester skins. Bending results revealed the interest of using sandwich with short flax shives based core as a competitive structure to the reference material.

1 INTRODUCTION

Diverse varieties of plant fibres have been investigated for composite reinforcement including hemp, bagasse, sisal and flax [1-2]. Among them, flax fibers have shown excellent specific mechanical performances and are being considered as a potential candidate to replace glass fibres [3]. Nevertheless, the valuation of the whole plant of flax is reduced essentially to the exploitation of the fibres [4-6], for the manufacture of structures used in various applications notably the transport. Flax shives which are the woody core generated as a waste by-product from the flax scutching process, possess low bulk density [7]. So, they can potentially be used for manufacturing composites such as particleboard [8-10].

In the context of sustainable development and valorization of local resources, innovative lightweight sandwich structures were developed for transportation and road applications. The skins and core were made respectively of flax fibres reinforced bio-based epoxy (GreenPoxy56) and flax shives particleboard. A reference material used for comparison consists in a sandwich structure made of a commercial honeycomb core (Nidaplast 8 RI) and glass fibres reinforced unsaturated polyester skins, typically used for truck walls and floors.

The main objective of this work is to investigate experimentally the quasi-static bending behavior of both the innovative flax sandwich structure and the reference material, in order to evaluate the potential of flax sandwich as a green and cheap structure.

The skins were elaborated by vacuum infusion method. However, three different elaboration processes were used for flax based sandwich structures. First one consists in one-shot vacuum infusion (VI), the second one, thermo-compression (TC) and third one, vacuum bag molding (VM). The objective was to find the most satisfactory method in terms of adhesion between skins and core, lightness and stiffness.

Microscopic observations using the SEM and X-ray microtomography revealed that one-shot vacuum infusion was not appropriate for the flax shives cores because pores between shives were entirely impregnated by the resin. The obtained particleboards and therefore sandwich structures were

too heavy. In fact, the use of this process with this type of core required further development. Thus, only thermo-compression and vacuum bag were used for flax based sandwich manufacturing. The reference structures were elaborated by one-shot vacuum infusion process.

2 MATERIALS

In this study, sandwich panels with flax shives particleboard core and skins made of flax fibres reinforced GreenPoxy 56 resin were elaborated in order to compare their mechanical properties with those of the reference material.

The reference one consists in a sandwich structure made of a commercial honeycomb core (Nidaplast 8 RI) and glass fibres reinforced unsaturated polyester skins.

Both flax and glass based skins were made of unidirectional fabrics, and were purchased from respectively Depestele and Chomarat textiles industries.

Epoxy adhesive films SA 70 from Gurit were used to bond flax based skins to the cores.

3 MANUFACTURING METHODS

3.1 Flax shives core

Particleboards with density of 500 kg/m³ and with two shives sizes were tested, in order to determine their effects on panels' properties. On one hand, the flax shives as obtained (LS) were sieved between two sieves of diameter 4 mm and 1 mm. The residue in the 1 mm sieve was used for the fabrication of particleboards. On the other hand, flax shives were crushed to 2mm of particle length (SS). Epoxy resin (20 % w/w) was mixed with flax shives (80 % w/w) and thermo-compressed at 90 °C for 10 minutes.

3.2 Skins

3.2.1 Flax composite

Flax fibre reinforced GreenPoxy56 resin were elaborated using vacuum infusion process. The skins were made with four layers of fabric at [0°/90°/90°/0°] configuration. First, the UD were oven dried at 90 ° C for 3 hours. Then, four layers were superimposed on a mold previously waxed and covered with a peel ply, a net bleeder and a vacuum bag. The GreenPoxy56 resin was catalyzed by the SD8822, suitable for the vacuum infusion process in terms of fluidity and crosslinking time. The infusion was performed under a depression equal to 0.5 bar, which was maintained until the polymerization of the resin. The demoulding was done after 24 hours. The mean fibre volume fraction was equal to 30%.

3.2.2 Glass composite

As a constituent of the sandwich structure, glass unsaturated polyester composite skins were elaborated using vacuum infusion process and characterized. The skins were made with four layers of fabric at [0°/90°/90°/0°] configuration. The same steps followed during the manufacture of the flax composites, apart the drying of the fibres one, were kept for the glass composites. The mean fibre volume fraction was equal to 42%.

3.3 Flax based sandwich structure

3.3.1 Vacuum bag molding

One cured skin was positioned at the bottom of the mold and covered by two epoxy adhesive film SA 70 (250g.m⁻²). Then, the flax shives core was placed and covered by two SA 70 and finally by a second cured skin. Vacuum bag was placed over the stack and air was removed. The vacuum of about 1 bar was maintained during curing the adhesive film at 100°C for 2 hours.

3.3.2 Thermo-compression molding

Applying the same stacking than in the Vacuum Bag, all the constituents of the sandwich were placed between two heated plates, and then pressed at 100°C for 2 hours. This choice of temperature and time curing cycle was imposed by the SA 70 specifications.

3.4 Quality inspection

In this work, microscopic observations using the SEM and X-ray micro-tomography were used to inspect and highlight, on one hand defects in flax shives particleboards and flax based sandwich structures. On the other hand, to identify the appropriate manufacturing process, which ensures a good adhesion between skins and core. It was observed that short flax shives particleboards are more homogeneous than long flax shives ones, which presents some empty spaces between particles. X-ray micro-tomography acquisitions revealed that one-shot vacuum infusion was not appropriate for the flax shives cores because pores between shives were entirely impregnated by the resin of flax sandwich. Following this, only thermo-compression and vacuum bag molding were used for flax based sandwich manufacturing. However, some samples made by the technique of vacuum bag were retired because of their poor adhesion between skins and core, which resulted in peeling.

4 MECHANICAL TESTS

It is interesting to characterize each component of the sandwich structure separately in order to better understand the behaviour of the whole structure. For this, tensile tests have been carried out on the skins according to ASTM D3039 standard. The laminates were cut in different orientations of fibres 0° and 90° with respect to the direction of traction, in order to determine the longitudinal and transverse modulus of elasticity. Then compression and shearing tests were done on the manufactured particleboards according to ASTM C365 and ASTM C273 standards respectively. Finally, all the sandwich structures were subjected only to three-point static bending tests according to ASTM C393 in order to determine their equivalent flexural and shear rigidity, noted respectively as (D) and (N) by the method of varying the span length (L). All the bending tests were conducted until the break. Then the force-displacement responses and failure modes were analyzed and compared between the innovative sandwich structure and the reference material. All the tests were performed using INSTRON universal testing machine type 5867. For each test, at least four specimens were tested under room conditions of temperature and humidity (~20°C, ~55% HR).

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Tensile behavior of composite skins

The stress-strain curves in the longitudinal direction presented in (Fig.1) are representative of the set of curves obtained for the GreenPoxy56 specimens and the skins made of Flax/GP 56 and Glass/PL. The analysis of these curves highlights an elastic behaviour of both resin GP 56 and Glass/PL skins with a modulus of elasticity equal respectively to 3580 MPa and 17556 MPa, before breaking abruptly for a slight deformation of 1.1% and 1.3% respectively.

The reinforcement of the GreenPoxy56 by unidirectional flax fibres at [0°,90°,90°,0°] configuration shows a nonlinear behaviour, identified by 3 different zones: A first very short linear zone, which corresponds to the reorganization of the cellulose fibrils. This zone allows to determine the apparent modulus of elasticity. Then, a nonlinear zone accompanied by a fall of the modulus of elasticity, which corresponds to an elasto-visco-plastic deformation of the individual flax fibres and more specifically of the S2 layer of the secondary wall [11]. Finally, the curve resumes its linearity until breaking. In this study, the Young's modulus is determined from the first linear zone of the curves, and is worth 11.2 GPa. All tensile results are summarized in (Table 1).

Figure 1: Tensile Stress-Strain curves of the resin GP 56 and the skins Flax/GP 56 and Glass/PL.

Type of Samples	E_L (MPa)	E_T (MPa)	σ_{TL} (MPa)	σ_{TT} (MPa)	ϵ_{TL} (%)
<i>GreenPoxy 56</i>	3580±212	-	35±4	-	1.1±0.2
<i>Flax/GP56</i>	11209±200	11206±637	97±7	96±12	1.3±0.14
<i>Glass/PL</i>	17556±1800	15285±128	221±16	302±30	1.3±0.6

Table 1: Summary of the mechanical properties of GreenPoxy56, Flax/GP56 and Glass/PL laminates determined after tensile tests.

In order to compare the mechanical tensile properties of flax and glass composites, specific properties were determined by dividing the mechanical characteristics by the density of the composites. The densities of the laminates were calculated according to the law of mixture. The results are presented in the form of histograms as shown in (Fig. 2).

It is noted that the Flax/GP 56 composites have excelled in specific elastic properties. However, the Glass/PL laminates have presented higher specific strength.

Figure 2: Evolution of the specific mechanical properties of Flax/GP56 laminates compared to the reference Glass/PL ones.

5.2 Mechanical behavior of flax shives based particleboards

In the context of this study, compression, shear and three-point static bending tests, as possible loading modes of the sandwich core, were carried out on long flax shives based particleboards. (Table 2) presents the results obtained, accompanied by the properties of Nidaplast 8 RI announced by the supplier. It is noted that for such particleboard density 500 kg/m^3 , considered as low according to ANSI A208.1-1999 standard, and such thickness 10 mm, the mechanical properties of the fabricated panels are high compared to those of the commercialized Nidaplast 8RI, the reference core. Even referring to results in the literature on particleboards, it seems that flax shives based panels have satisfactory mechanical properties [8], [12]. This is mainly revealing an improved bonding between shives and the GP56 resin.

Properties	Materials	
	Long flax shives particleboard	Nidaplast 8 RI
Density	500 kg/m^3	65 kg/m^3
Thickness	10 mm	20 mm
Compressive modulus	59MPa	40MPa
MOE	1517 MPa	-
MOR	8.4 MPa	-
Shear modulus	9.11 MPa	9MPa
Shear strength	1.1 MPa	0.4MPa

Table 2: Mechanical properties of long flax shives particleboard and Nidaplast 8RI.

5.3 Three-point static bending behavior of sandwich structure

In the case of three-point static bending by varying the span length L , the plot of the ratio of the deflection W under an applied load P , divided by the span length L as a function of the square of span length allows to obtain a straight line. The equivalent flexural and shear rigidity, noted respectively as

(D) and (N) of sandwich structure, are respectively determined across the slope and the ordinate at the origin of the straight line, according to the following equation:

$$\frac{W}{PL} = \frac{1}{48D} L^2 + \frac{1}{4N} \quad (1)$$

In this study, we seek to compare the bending response between the manufactured sandwich structures and the reference one. According to NF T 54-606 standard, the span length is dependent on the total thickness of the structure and must vary between 10 and 20 times the thickness of the specimen in order to observe the evolution of its stiffness. In fact, for the determination of shear properties, the span length must be equal to 10 times the total thickness of the specimen. However, bending properties require span lengths near to 20 times the total thickness. Given the difference in thickness between the fabricated and the reference sandwiches, the span length is no longer considered as a constant to respect for the two materials to be able to compare. But rather, the ratio between L and t called slenderness, which has been considered. In this study, the slenderness varies between 10 and 16 for flax based sandwich, restricted by the length of the manufactured core, which depends on dimensions of the disposable mold in the laboratory. However, it extends until 20 for reference material. Thus, the evolution of the ratio $W/(PL)$ as a function of L^2/t^2 is presented for the different manufactured sandwich and the reference one in (Fig. 3). Besides, the evolution of the stiffness P/W as a function of L^2/t^2 is presented in (Fig. 4).

Figure 3: Evolution of the ratio $W/(PL)$ as a function of L^2/t^2 for flax and reference sandwiches.

Figure 4: Evolution of the stiffness P/W as a function of L^2/t^2 for flax and reference sandwiches.

Through these curves, several remarks can be made. At first, it is noted that the sandwiches F/SS-TC are more rigid than the other flax based ones. Then, sandwiches made by thermo compression process are more rigid than the ones made by vacuum bag molding. Also, for the same manufacturing process, the sandwiches with short shives-based core are more rigid than the ones with long shives based core. As regards the reference material, it can be seen that for short span lengths, it is less rigid than sandwiches made by thermo-compression and those with short shives based core made by vacuum bag molding. Nevertheless by increasing L , its stiffness increases more and more. This is better verified through the measured equivalent rigidity D and shear rigidity N summarized in (Table 3).

Sandwich Materials	$D \cdot 10^6$ [N.mm ²]	N [kN]
Glass/Nidaplast	213	13.7
F/SS-TC	54.5	126
F/LS-TC	49.8	29.3
F/SS-VM	49	28.2
F/LS-VM	42	14

Table 3: Summary of flexural and shear rigidity measured for flax and reference sandwiches.

5.4 Failure analysis

In this study during flexural tests, different failure modes were observed depending on the core, the manufacturing process and the span length used. These modes of rupture are presented in (Fig. 5).

In the case of flax based sandwich structures made by thermo-compression, we notice that the rupture take place always in the core. This is due to the weak shear properties of the core compared to those of the skins and interface made by SA 70. Also, it is noted that cracks initiate in long flax shives based core for small deflexion compared to short flax shives based one. However, in the case of flax based sandwich structures made by vacuum bag molding, the failure was caused by delamination between skin and core. This is due to the poor adhesion between the skins and core, caused by the manufacturing process.

In the case of Glass/Nidaplast sandwich, rupture depends essentially on span length: For short distances between supports, we notice a failure by core shearing. While for longer distances, the rupture was caused by debonding between glass fibre and resin at the top skins. This is due to the honeycomb Nidaplast, which has low shear rigidity and high flexural properties.

In all the cases, the different observed failure modes comply with measured results.

Figure 5: Observed failure modes: (a), (b) Shear of the core for sandwich made by thermo-compression. (c) Delamination between skin and core in sandwich made by vacuum bag molding. (d) Shear of the Nidaplast. (e) Debonding between glass fibre and resin.

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, quasi static bending behaviour of innovative flax based sandwich structures and mechanical characteristics of its components were investigated.

Tensile tests have shown that flax based skins have high specific elastic properties compared to those of glass based skins.

The analysis of failure modes have shown the interference of manufacturing processes and flax shives sizes in the bending behaviour of flax based sandwich structures, through the quality of adhesion between skins and core.

The stiffness of sandwich with short flax shives based core made by thermo-compression was high compared to that of the reference sandwich, typically used for truck walls and floors. Nevertheless, this type of sandwich with short flax shives based core require more optimization in terms of cohesion between particles in the core , in order to further improve the flexural rigidity of whole the structure .

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